

First Canadian Living Lab Summit

Montreal, 6 – 7 November 2023

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS from the First Canadian Living Lab Summit Montreal 6-7 November 2023

Executive Summary

The European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) was established in 2006 by the European Commission under the Finnish Presidency. It aims to foster global development of Living Labs as open innovation ecosystems that emphasize co-creation and cross-border & cross-sectoral collaboration. ENoLL's mission is to offer value to its members and stakeholders by enhancing capacities and knowledge. While primarily a European network with 80% of its members based in Europe, it has a global reach, including significant engagement in Canada.

Canada's involvement with ENoLL dates back to the early days, notably with the RehabMaLL, the first Living Lab in Rehabilitation, founded in Quebec in 2011. This initiative was supported by the Fonds Recherche Quebec Santé (FRQS) and the Centre for Interdisciplinary Research in Rehabilitation (CRIR). Since then, the presence and impact of Living Labs have expanded dramatically in Canada. The country now boasts over 100 Living Labs across diverse sectors including environment, agriculture, forestry, marine life, urban development, sustainability, and health. These Labs are situated in various settings such as universities, research centers, and community-based organizations.

The inaugural Canadian Living Lab Summit, held in Montreal in November 2023, was hosted by McGill University and co-organized by ENoLL, McGill, and the University of Montreal. The summit provided a unique platform for participants to exchange ideas, forge collaborations, and strengthen the Living Lab ecosystem. This event highlighted the vibrant Living Lab activities across Canada and emphasized opportunities for cross-border and cross-sectoral partnerships, particularly between Canadian and European Living Labs. The summit's objectives included promoting the Living Lab methodology, showcasing Canadian initiatives, supporting networking and knowledge exchange, and drafting Policy Recommendations for Canadian Policy Makers.

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POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

Needs of Living Labs in Canada: Supporting a Living Lab Culture while/by Diversifying Funding Opportunities

Living Labs (LLs) in Canada play a crucial role in fostering innovation and collaboration to address real-world challenges. However, to thrive and maximize their impact, LLs require greater support from Funding Agencies. This document outlines key areas where Funding Agencies can provide such support, creating a more robust and impactful ecosystem for LLs as an outcome of the “First Canadian Living Labs Summit” organized by McGill University, University of Montreal, and ENoLL – European Network of Living Labs.

Beyond traditional project-based grants, LLs require a more diverse funding landscape. Dedicated funding programs specifically designed for LL initiatives would be highly beneficial. Additionally, support for partnership-based research projects that align with the core principles of the LL approach, even when not explicitly named as such, is crucial. These core principles include collaboration, co-creation, and a focus on real-life environment problem-solving. Funding Agencies can also recognize and fund programs that embody these principles, fostering a broader understanding of the LL approach.

1. **Promote Funding Flexibility:** Prioritize allocating resources to support community-based research and Living Labs (LLs) initiatives, acknowledging their role in driving innovation and addressing real-world challenges. Encourage funding that allows for flexibility in project design and implementation, requesting collaboration between researchers, industries, public administrations, communities, and end-users. Emphasize the importance of funding models that support co-creation and co-design processes, enabling stakeholders to actively participate in shaping research agendas and outcomes.
2. **Enhance Intersectoral Collaboration (quadruple/quintuple helix):** Allocate resources to support initiatives that foster collaboration between different sectors, including academia, industry, government, and communities. Recognize the value of interdisciplinary approaches in addressing complex societal challenges and breaking down silos between disciplines. Encourage partnerships that leverage diverse expertise and perspectives, maximizing the impact of research outcomes and promoting innovation.
3. **Prioritize Interdisciplinary Research:** Incentivize projects that promote interdisciplinary research approaches, bringing together experts from various fields to address multifaceted issues. Allocate resources to support collaborative efforts that bridge traditional disciplinary boundaries and encourage open innovative solutions. Emphasize the importance of funding programs that promote cross-disciplinary collaboration and knowledge exchange, driving impactful research outcomes.
4. **Invest in Capacity Building:** Allocate resources for capacity building initiatives to promote the LL approach and to empower researchers, communities, and stakeholders involvement. Support training programs, workshops, and collaborative networks that enhance skills, knowledge, and

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expertise in co-creation and co-design methodologies. Recognize the importance of investing in human capital to build sustainable research ecosystems and foster a culture of innovation and collaboration.

5. **Support Sustainable Living Labs Infrastructure:** Recognize the critical role of infrastructure in supporting the long-term sustainability of LL initiatives. Allocate resources for the development of physical spaces, staffing, and other necessary resources to support ongoing LL activities. Emphasize the importance of investing in infrastructure that enables collaboration, knowledge sharing, and innovation, ensuring the continued effectiveness of LL initiatives over time.
6. **Revise Evaluation Criteria:** Reevaluate the criteria used to assess research impact, moving beyond traditional metrics like impact factors and publications. Consider alternative methods for evaluating the success of LL initiatives, such as community engagement, knowledge mobilization, and societal impact. Emphasize the importance of measuring outcomes that reflect the real-world impact of research, including its relevance to communities and stakeholders.
7. **Facilitate Knowledge Mobilization:** Support initiatives that utilize creative strategies for disseminating research results and knowledge generated from LLs to diverse audiences. Allocate resources for communication channels such as plays, musicals, books, and digital platforms that reach broader communities effectively. Emphasize the importance of engaging with stakeholders to ensure that research findings are accessible, relevant, and actionable.
8. **Promote Open Science Principles:** Support the adoption of Open Science principles within LL initiatives, promoting transparency, inclusivity, and collaboration in research practices. Allocate resources for the development of policies and infrastructure that facilitate the involvement of diverse communities, including Indigenous perspectives, in research processes. Encourage practices that promote data sharing, reproducibility, and ethical conduct, fostering a culture of openness and accountability.
9. **Ensure Stakeholder Engagement:** Emphasize the importance of stakeholder engagement in LL initiatives, recognizing communities, industry partners, and various stakeholders as valuable contributors to the research process. Create opportunities for meaningful dialogue and collaboration among stakeholders, ensuring that research priorities are aligned with the needs and interests of end-users. Encourage inclusive decision-making processes that promote equity, diversity, and mutual learning.
10. **Encourage International Collaboration:** Foster partnerships and collaboration on LL initiatives at the international level, recognizing the global nature of many societal challenges. Facilitate knowledge exchange, funding opportunities, and best practice sharing between countries, leveraging diverse perspectives and expertise in LL research. Encourage cross-border collaborations that address shared challenges and promote innovation on a global scale.